

ENVIRONMENT CHALLENGES AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT THROUGH THE USE OF TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract:

Earth, also called the world, and less frequently Gaia, is the third farthest planet from the Sun. The densest planet in the Solar System, and the only planet to support life in the entire universe. The life on Earth arose around 3.5 billion years ago. Earth's biodiversity has expanded continuously, is currently

home to 10-14 million species of life, including 7.2 billion humans who depend upon its biosphere and minerals. Earth's lithosphere is divided into several rigid tectonic plates that migrate across the surface over periods of millions of years. Seventy-one percent of Earth's surface is covered with water, with the remainder consisting of continents and islands that comprises of lakes and other sources of water that contribute to the hydrosphere. Earth's poles are mostly covered with ice that includes the solid ice of the Antarctic ice sheet and the sea ice of the polar ice packs. Earth's interior remains active

with a solid iron inner core, a liquid outer core that generates the magnetic field, and a thick layer of relatively solid mantle separated by Mohorovicic discontinuity.

Introduction

The distance of Earth from the Sun, as well as its orbital eccentricity, rate of rotation, axial tilt, geological history, sustaining atmosphere and protective magnetic field all contribute to the current climatic conditions at the surface. A planet's life forms are sometimes said to form a biosphere. The biosphere is divided into a number of biomes, inhabited by broadly similar type of flora and fauna. Earth's provides basic necessities to every species that are required to support life. Earth provides natural resources that are lifeline to human beings for useful purposes. Some of these are non-renewable resources, such as fossil fuels, that are difficult to replenish on a short time scale. Large deposits of fossil fuels are obtained from Earth's crust, consisting of coal, petroleum and natural gas. These deposits are used by humans both for energy production and as feedstock for chemical production. Mineral ore bodies have also been formed within the crust through a process of ore genesis, resulting

from actions of magmatism, erosion and plate tectonics. Earth's biosphere produces many useful biological products for humans, including food, wood, pharmaceuticals, oxygen, and the recycling of many organic wastes. The land-based ecosystem depends upon topsoil and fresh water, and the oceanic ecosystem depends upon dissolved nutrients washed down from the land. Large areas of Earth's surface are subject to extreme weather such as tropical cyclones, hurricanes, or typhoons that dominate life in some areas. From 1980 to 2000, these events caused an average of 11,800 deaths per year. Many places are prone to earthquakes, landslides, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, tornadoes, sinkholes, blizzards, floods, droughts, wildfires, and other calamities and disasters.

Many localized areas are subject to human-made pollution of the air and water, acid rain and toxic substances, loss of vegetation (overgrazing, deforestation, desertification), loss of wildlife, species extinction, soil degradation, soil depletion, erosion, and introduction of species. According to the United Nations, a scientific consensus exists linking human activities to global warming due to industrial carbon dioxide emissions. This is predicted to produce changes such as the melting of glaciers and ice sheets, more extreme temperature ranges, significant changes in weather and a global rise in average sea levels.

From medieval periods to modern era of 21st century, a lot has changed, humans have grown to become brightest and most intelligent species on the planet Earth. We, human beings try to invent, innovate and build new things. We always try to find the solutions to the most difficult problems in the universe. We have tried to achieve the maximum growth in shortest time possible. We, all have tried to change the face of the earth, to suite ourselves according to our needs and values, but in doing so we have destroyed Earth's biology.

For our own benefits, we have eroded away the habitual environment and overexploited the natural resources. According to The United States Census Bureau estimates that the world population exceeded 7 billion on March 12, 2012. According to a separate estimate by the United Nations Population Fund, it reached this milestone on October 31, 2011. Overpopulation is a big issue it has led to many environment and climatic changes, most of human settlement, till now is unorganized, whether it is urban area or rural area. According to Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation the total population in India was last recorded at 1238.9 million people in 2014 from 359.0 million in 1950, changing 245 percent during the last 50 years. Population in India averaged 744.18 Million from 1950 until 2014, reaching an all-time high of 1238.89 Million in 2014 and a record low of 359 Million in 1950. The population of India represents 17.99 percent of the world's total population which arguably means that one person in every 6 people on the planet is a resident of India. Most of people in India live in rural areas, most of which is unorganized settlement. Unorganized settlement has led to deforestation, extinction of rare Indian Population, over the years animal species and has put immense pressure on the surface of the Earth due to which there are floods, earthquakes, landslides etc. Like recent floods in Jammu and Kashmir state for which Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced a relief package of 1000crore and 2013 floods in state of Uttarakhand

Government of several countries have adopted many policies for settlement of human population. They have used advance technologies like GPS(Global Positioning System), Satellite imagery and Super Computers for mapping of Earth's surface and deciding whether it is having required habitat or not. Several governments around the world like Federal government of USA, Government of India, etc, use GIS (Geographic Information System). GIS is a system designed to capture, store, manipulate, analyze, manage, and present all types geographical data. Several state governments of India has implemented GIS systems for analyzing, storing of data and improving the quality of life. The natural environment encompasses all living and non-living things occurring naturally on Earth or some region thereof. It is an environment that encompasses the interaction of all living species. Climate, weather, and natural resources that affect human survival and economic activity and there is an additional focus on the present generation's responsibility to regenerate, maintain and improve planetary resources for use by future generations [1]

Biodiversity is the degree of variation of life. It is a measure of the variety of organisms present in different ecosystems. This can refer to genetic variation, ecosystem variation, or species variation (number of species) within an area, biome, or planet. Terrestrial biodiversity tends to be highest near

the equator, which seems to be the result of the warm climate and high primary productivity. Biodiversity is not distributed evenly on Earth. It is the richest in the tropics. Marine biodiversity tends to be highest along coasts in the Western Pacific, where sea surface temperature is highest and in the mid-latitudinal band in all oceans. There are latitudinal gradients in species diversity. Biodiversity generally tends to cluster in hotspots, and has been increasing through time but will be likely to slow in the future. Rainforests are an example of biodiversity on the planet and typically possess a great deal of species diversity. This is the Gambia River in Senegal's Niokolo-Koba National Park. Generally, there is an increase in biodiversity from the poles to the tropics. Thus localities at lower latitudes have more species than localities at higher latitudes. This is often referred to as the latitudinal gradient in species diversity. Several ecological mechanisms may contribute to the gradient, but the ultimate factor behind many of them is the greater mean temperature at the equator compared to that of the poles. Even though terrestrial biodiversity declines from the equator to the poles, some studies claim that this characteristic is unverified in aquatic ecosystems, especially in marine ecosystem. Both ecoefficiency and socio efficiency are concerned with increasing economic sustainability however, Dyllick and Hockerts point out that eco effectiveness, socio effectiveness, sufficiency and ecoequity are needed for sustainable development[2] The latitudinal distribution of parasites does not follow this rule. A biodiversity hotspot is a region with a high level of endemic species that is under threat from humans. The term hotspot was introduced in 1988 by Dr. Sabina Virk. While hotspots are spread all over the world, majority are forest areas and most are located in the tropics.

India has some of the world's most biodiverse regions. The political boundaries of India encompass a wide range of Eco zones- desert, high mountains, highlands, tropical and temperate forests, swamplands, plains, grasslands as well as island archipelago. It hotspots: The Western Ghats, the Himalayas and the Indo-Burma region. These hotspots have numerous endemic species. The region is also heavily influenced by summer monsoon that cause major seasonal changes in vegetation and habitat. India forms a large part of the Indomalayan biogeographical zone and many of the flora and fauna forms show Malayan affinities with only a few being to the Indian region. The flora and fauna of India have been studied and recorded from early times in folk traditions and later by researchers following more formal scientific approaches[3]. Game laws are reported from third century BC. A little under 5% of this total area is formally classified under protected areas.

India is a home to several well-known large mammals, including the Asian Elephants, Bengal Tiger, Asiatic Lion, Leopard and Indian Rhinoceros. Some of these animals are engrained in culture, often being associated with deities. These large mammals are important for wildlife tourism in India, and several national parks and wildlife sanctuaries cater to these needs. The popularity of these charismatic animals helped greatly in conservation efforts in India. The tiger has been particularly important, and Project Tiger, started in 1972, was a major effort to conserve the Tiger and its habitats. Project Elephant, though less known started in 1992 and works for Elephant protection. Most of India's rhinos today survive in the Kaziranga National Park. Some other well-known large Indian mammals are: ungulates such as the water buffalo, nilgai, gaur and several species of deer.

Many smaller animals such as macaques, langurs and mongoose species are especially well-known due to their ability to live close to or inside urban areas. There are about 2,546 species of fishes (about 11% of the world species) found in Indian waters. About 197 species of amphibians (4.4% of the world total) and more than 408 reptile species (6 % of the world total) are found in India. Among these groups the highest levels of endemism are found in the amphibians. There are about 1,250 species of bird from India, with some variations, depending on taxonomic treatments, accounting for about 12% of the world species[4]. The World Conservation Monitoring Centre gives an estimate of about 15,000 species of flowering plants in India Biodiversity of India.

The Western Ghats are a chain of hills that run along the western edge of peninsular India. Their proximity to the ocean and through orographic effect, they receive high rainfall. These regions have most deciduous forest and rain forest.

The regions show high species diversity as well as high levels of endemism. Nearly 77% of the amphibians and 62% of the reptile species found here. [5]The region shows biogeographical affinities to the Malayan region, and the Sapura hypothesis proposed by Sunder Lal Hora suggests that the hill chains of Central India may have once formed a connection with the forests of northeastern India and into the Indo-Malayan region.

The Eastern Himalayas is the region encompassing Bhutan, northeastern India and southern, central and eastern Nepal. The region is geologically young and shows high altitudinal variation. It has nearly 163 globally threatened species including the one-horned rhinoceros, the Wild Asian water buffalo and in all 45 mammals, 50 birds, 17 reptiles, 12 amphibians and 36 plant species. The relict dragonfly is an endangered species found here with the only other species in the genus being found in Japan. The region is also home to the Himalayan newt, the only salamander species found within Indian limits.

During the early Tertiary period, the Indian tableland, what is today peninsular India, was a large island. Prior to becoming an island it was connected to the African region. During the tertiary period this island was separated from the Asian mainland by a shallow sea.[6] The Himalayan region and the

greater part of Tibet lay under this sea. The movement of the Indian subcontinent into the Asian landmass created the great Himalayan ranges and raised the sea bed into what is today the plains of northern India.

Once connected to the Asian mainland, many species moved into India. The Himalayan were created in several upheavals. The Siwaliks were formed in the last and the largest number of fossils of the Tertiary period are found in these ranges.

The Siwaliks fossils include mastodons, hippopotamus, rhinoceros, a large four-horned ruminant, horses, giraffes, camels, bison and a host of other mammals. Many fossil tree species have been found in the intertrappean beds including *Grewtoxylofrim* Eocene and *Heritieroxylokeralensis* from the middle Miocene in Kerala and at many other places. The discovery of *Glissopteris* fern fossils from India and Antarctica led to the discovery of Gondwanaland and led to the greater understanding of continental drift. Fossil Cycads are known from India while seven Cycad species continue to survive in India. Several small mammal fossils have been recorded in the intertrappean beds, however larger mammals are mostly unknown. The only major primate fossils have been from the nearby region of Myanmar.

The exploitation of land and forest resources by humans along with hunting and trapping for food and sport has led to the extinction of many species in India in recent times.[7]

Norable mammals which became or are presumed extinct within the country itself include the Indian/ Asiatic cheetah, Javan rhinoceros and Sumantran rhinoceros. While some of these mammal species are confirmed extinct, there have been many smaller animal and plant species whose status is harder to determine. Many species have not been seen since their description. *Hubbardiaheptaneuron*, a species of grass that grew in the spray one of the Jog Falls prior to the construction of the Linganamakki reservoir, was thought to be extinct but a were discovered near Kolhapur.

Some species of birds have gone extinct in recent times, including the pink-headed duck (Dodo) and the Himalayan quail. A species of warbler known earlier from a single specimen collected by Allan Octavian Hume from near Rampur in Himachal Pradesh was rediscovered after 139 years in Thailand. Similarly, the Jerdon's courser named after the zoologist Thomas C. Jerdon who discovered it in 1848, was rediscovered in 1986 by Bharat Bhushan, an ornithologist at the Bombay Natural History Society after being thought to be extinct.

Though India currently is considered a mega diverse country with many of the world's species sadly, hunting is thing which has played a crucial part in the lessening of the number of animals. One of the most effected animal is the Tiger.[8] Also, there are doubts about the flawed method of counting of population of Tiger in India. The rhino found mostly in Kaziranga too is depleting fast for the enormous demand. The back seat has been given to the fauna by the Indian Government, and the fines that have to be paid are mostly lesser than the money they earn by the poaching. If something is not fast, then many species shall instantly become extinct and others in due course. Many people and even companies have expressed strong concern over such topics.

Not only, because of exploitation of natural resources led to an extinction of flora and fauna, also there is a drastic change in climatic conditions. Climate change is a change in the statistical distribution of weather pattern when that change lasts for an extended period of time (i.e. decades or millions of years). Climate change is caused by various factors such as biotic processes, variation in solar radiation received by Earth, plate tectonics and volcanic eruptions. Certain human activities have also been identified as significant causes of recent climate change, often referred to as “Global Warming.”

Scientists actively work to understand past and future climate by using observations and theoretical models. A climate record- extending deep into the Earth’s past – has been assembled, and continues to be built up, based on geological evidence from borehole temperature profiles, core removed from deep accumulations of ice, floral and faunal records, glacial and proglacial processes, stable-isotope and other analyses of sediment layers, and records of past sea levels. More recent data are provided by the instrument record.

In the context of climatic variation, anthropogenic factors are human activities which affect the climate. The scientific consensus on climate change is “that climate is changing and that these changes are in a large part caused by human activities,” and it “is largely irreversible.” Of most concern in these anthropogenic factors is the increase in CO₂ levels due to emission from fossil fuel combustion, followed by aerosols (particular matter in the atmosphere) and the CO₂ released by cement manufacture. Other factors, including land use, ozone depletion, animal agriculture and deforestation, are also of concern in the roles they play- both separately and in conjunction with other factors- in affecting climate, microclimate, and measures of climate variables. Evidence for climatic change is taken from a variety of sources that can be used to reconstruct past climates. Reasonably complete global records of surface temperature are available beginning from the mid-late 19th century. For earlier periods, most of the evidence is indirect- climatic changes are inferred from changes in proxies, indicators that reflect climate, such as vegetation, ice cores, sea level changes and glacial geology.

Over the years, there is an increase in the global temperature of Earth. In recent times Earth’s global temperature has risen by 1 degree Celsius. Glaciers are considered among the most sensitive indicators of climate change. Their size is determined by a mass balance between snow input and melt

output. As temperature warm, glaciers melts down very speedily. The World Glacier Monitoring Service collects data annually on glacier retreat and glacier mass balance. From this data, glaciers worldwide have been found to be shrinking significantly, with strong glacier retreats in the 1940s, stable or growing conditions during the 1920s and 1970s, and again retreating from the mid-1980s to present. The decline in Arctic sea ice, both in extent and thickness, over the last several decades is further evidence for rapid climate change. One of the major factor of climate change is “global warming”. The potential dangers of global warming are being increasingly studied by a wide global consortium of scientists. These scientists are increasingly concerned about the potential long-term effects of global warming on our natural and in the planet. Of particular concern is how climatic change and global warming caused by anthropogenic, or human-made releases of greenhouse gases most notably carbon dioxide, can act interactively, and have adverse effects upon the planet, its natural environment and human existences. It is clear the planet is warming, and warming rapidly. Efforts have been increasingly focused on the mitigation of greenhouse gases that are causing climatic changes, on developing adaptive strategies to global warming, to assist humans, other animal and plant species, ecosystems, regions and nations in adjusting to the effects of the global warming. A significantly profound challenge is to identify the natural environmental dynamics in contrast to environmental changes not within natural variations. A common solution is to adapt a static view neglecting natural variations.

To meet the environment and climatic challenges, we need to have a sustainable development and need to use environmental friendly energies and technologies, like solar energy, nanotechnology, etc. We have already started using renewable resources and has made significant progress through it, like advancement in making solar powered planes, using nano technology to build the body of cars and planes using carbon fiber instead of aluminum (carbon fiber is lighter than aluminum which help in less fuel consumption and better mileage) , etc.

Through the use nanotechnology we can we would be using less or reusing the natural resources. There are many applications of nanotechnology which could be used to meet environment challenges. Nanotechnology is already in use in some industries. In general, in developing countries, the share of public investment in total nanotechnology R&D basket is relatively greater in comparison to private sector[8]. Although the growing importance of private sector cannot be underestimated, but given that technology base for nanotechnology being in an embryonic phase, industry would not be able to sustain the research effort needed for the establishment of scientific and technological infrastructure for sustainable development.

Future of human race is in its own hands. Now we, humans have to decide which way we need to go.

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